

IMPLEMENTATION OF INTER-SUBJECT RELATIONS OF PHYSICS WITH CHEMISTRY AND BIOLOGY WHEN TEACHING STUDENTS OF THE PRESIDENTIAL SCHOOL OF UZBEKISTAN

Makhmudov Eshmirza Adinaevich

Termez Institute of Agro technologies and Innovative Development
Competitor of the Department of Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Humanities

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7312338>

Abstract: the paper deals with issues aimed at strengthening the fundamental nature of education, at preparing a comprehensively educated person, taking into account the requirements of society for the level of training of students. It has been proven that MPS is a form of coordination of two or more subjects, necessary in order to teach schoolchildren to study specific situations and solve practically significant tasks in learning and in life, to establish links between various subjects to ensure the integrity of the learning process and the acquisition of a knowledge system.

Key words: knowledge, integration, globalization, development, problem, education, quality, fundamentality, society, education, value, authority, profession, complex, requirements, model, standard.

Today, the explosion of knowledge, international integration and globalization create great opportunities for the development of each country and also bring many problems. The competition of countries in socio-economic development requires competitive human resources. As a result, many countries, including Uzbekistan, are constantly reforming the education system in order to improve its quality. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026, aimed at strengthening the fundamental nature of education, at preparing a comprehensively educated person, taking into account the requirements of society for the level of training of students. In order to form the knowledge and skills of school students, educate them in the spirit of devotion to national and universal values, increase the authority of the teaching profession and the quality of teachers, improve textbooks and educational and methodological complexes based on modern requirements, build modern models of public education institutions that meet international standards, as well as in accordance with the State program for the implementation of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.

It identifies 6 key areas: improving the quality of education based on advanced foreign experience, increasing the authority of the teaching profession, developing inclusive education, vocational guidance for students, improving infrastructure and digitalization of the sphere. Each of these areas consists of dozens of specific tasks. Also, in accordance with the presidential decree for the implementation of this program, "road maps" have been developed for each district and city. At the meeting, the Minister of Public Education reported on the work begun in this direction and plans for the next academic year.

At the meeting, instructions were given on the transformation of teacher education, improving admission to universities, increasing scientific potential and linking the

educational process with practice. During the discussion of the issues of improving the professional skills of teachers and teaching them new methods, it was pointed out that it is necessary to expand the activities of the Abdulla Avloni National Research Institute, to ensure close interaction between the institute and local pedagogical schools. A decision was made to introduce from the next academic year a system of professional certification of teachers of chemistry, biology, physics and mathematics in the “Year of Ensuring Human Interests and Development of the Mahalla”: it is planned to actively introduce new curricula and textbooks into practice: first in the lower grades, and then in the upper grades. The new educational program of general education in Uzbekistan provides for continuous education in the natural sciences.

At present, the system of natural science education in the schools of Uzbekistan has the following structure:

- natural sciences and social subjects (grades 1-4), basic sciences (grades 4 and 5) are studied in elementary school;
- An integrated course of natural science is studied in junior high school, containing material on physics, chemistry, biology (grades 7-9);
- in the senior classes (grades 10-11) students study separate subjects: physics, chemistry, biology.

Thus, in a general education school, natural science education is carried out in two stages:

Stage I (basic) - primary and junior high school.

Stage II - middle (high) school.

The science curriculum in elementary school involves a simple phenomenological approach to considering the properties of bodies and phenomena that students encounter in the world around them: in nature and in everyday life, which helps to create their initial physical representations. In junior high school, the content of the integrated natural science course includes knowledge of physics, chemistry, biology, organized in accordance with such content lines as matter, life, energy, Earth, sky. The content of this course reflects the general principles of the world of Nature (structure, diversity, interaction, systematization, laws of motion and transformation; the role of science in the development of society; the application of scientific knowledge in life).

The content of the natural science course includes thematic blocks (physics, chemistry, biology) and allows you to form knowledge about the principles, general laws of the natural world, the role of natural sciences in the development of society and ideas about the application of knowledge. This content is presented in linear logic with elements of centrism.

II stage (stage of vocational guidance): middle (high) school.

Natural science education is carried out mainly in the study of physics, chemistry and biology in grades 10 and 11. These are subjects from the group of natural science subjects that students choose according to their professional intentions, interests and abilities. The content of each subject guarantees the development of knowledge and practical skills based on the general abilities, knowledge and skills that were formed at the basic stage, and contributes to orientation towards a specific profession.

The new educational program of general education in Uzbekistan is aimed at solving one of the main tasks of the school - the formation of a comprehensively developed personality, which is characterized by creative activity, dynamic thinking and independence.

The solution of this problem involves the reflection in school education of the integration processes taking place in modern science and practice, which is possible, including through the implementation of interdisciplinary relations (ILS). Taking into account the MPS when teaching natural science subjects contributes to the enrichment and deepening of students' knowledge, the formation of a scientific worldview, ideas about the relationship of natural phenomena and its unity, a holistic natural-science picture of the world, the formation of skills to carry out independent cognitive activity, apply the knowledge gained in practical activities. Therefore, in the process of teaching in physics lessons, it is very important to establish the MPS with other natural science subjects: biology, physical geography, chemistry.

In the course of our ascertaining experiment, the purpose of which was to study the state of the problem of implementing the MPS of physics with chemistry and biology in the process of teaching students in schools in Uzbekistan, the following shortcomings were identified:

- the level of knowledge of students about the MPS and the ability to establish them is low;
- the level of knowledge of teachers about the MPS of physics with chemistry and biology is also low.

Teachers pay attention to the implementation of the MPS when teaching science to secondary school students, however, their activities do not fully meet the requirements for the implementation of these connections. In practice, teachers experience great difficulties because they do not have a theoretical basis for the implementation of the MPS. In recent years, Uzbek scientists have carried out research on the problem of improving the general education of Uzbekistan. The problem of integrating the content of education was touched upon in the works of Uzbek teachers and methodologists: Yu. Ganiev, B. Abdullaev, and others. The considered works do not reflect the implementation of the MPS of physics with biology and chemistry in teaching secondary school students in the context of the reform of Uzbek education. In the Russian Federation, this problem is considered in the works of didacticists and methodologists: I.D. Zvereva, I.K. Turysheva, D.M. Kiryushkina, Yu.I. Dika, V.N. Maksimova, V.N. Fedorova, A.V. Usova, as well as in dissertation research by Zh.V. Belyaeva, E.S. Valovich, V.V. Gubina, A.S. Gurieva, L.S. Dubitskaya, S.P. Zlobina, M.T. Rakhmatullina, M.Zh. Simonova, L.D. Ufimtseva and others.

An analysis of works on the problem under study showed that many authors consider MPS between two or three academic subjects (biology and physics; chemistry and physics; biology, chemistry and physics). The most significant for our study are the works of Yu. Ganiev, T. Toloaganov. Zh. Ikromova, N. Gaibullaeva and Z. Tozhieva. They discuss the problems of MPS biology with physics, physics with biology and chemistry in basic and secondary schools in Uzbekistan. However, the experience and research results of Uzbek scientists cannot be fully introduced into the teaching process at physics lessons in a secondary school in Uzbekistan.

Thus, there are contradictions between:

- the importance of the MPS of physics with chemistry and biology for the formation in students of a systematic knowledge, a scientific picture of the world, the ability to explain natural science phenomena and the ability to solve interdisciplinary problems and the lack of a methodology for the implementation of the MPS of physics with chemistry and biology in teaching secondary school students in Uzbekistan;

- the need to develop a model of the methodology for the implementation of the MPS of physics with chemistry and biology in teaching secondary school students and the lack of theoretical foundations for constructing this methodology.

These contradictions determine the relevance of the research topic: "Implementation of interdisciplinary connections between physics and chemistry and biology in teaching secondary school students in Uzbekistan. Naturally, what should be the methodology for implementing the MPS of physics with chemistry and biology when teaching secondary school students in Uzbekistan? Then it is necessary to develop a methodology for the implementation of the MPS of physics with chemistry and biology in teaching students in grades 10-11 of a secondary school in Uzbekistan. Our main task is to theoretically substantiate, develop and test methods for implementing the MPS of physics with chemistry and biology in teaching secondary school students in Uzbekistan.

Thus, when teaching physics on the basis of its connection with chemistry and biology, students will develop a systematic knowledge, the ability to explain natural science phenomena and the ability to solve interdisciplinary problems if:

- consider the implementation of the MPS in teaching physics as a didactic condition for the implementation of natural science education;
- the methodology for implementing the MPS of physics with chemistry and biology will be based on the use of problem-based and project-based teaching methods;
- the implementation of the MPS will be consistently carried out in the study of new material, in solving interdisciplinary problems, in the implementation of interdisciplinary projects.

Each teacher of physics of the presidential school in his practice defined the following tasks: to clearly recognize and understand the state of the problem of implementation in the process of teaching MPS of physics with biology and chemistry in pedagogical theory; To identify the state of the problem of implementing the MPS of physics with biology and chemistry in teaching students in schools in Uzbekistan; Theoretically substantiate and develop a model of the methodology for implementing the MPS of physics with other natural science subjects in teaching secondary school students.

Practice shows that in modern didactics there are several points of view on the status of MPS, and there is no single definition of this concept yet. Thus, MPS is a form of coordination of two or more subjects necessary to teach students to study specific situations and solve practically significant tasks in learning and in life, to establish links between different subjects to ensure the integrity of the learning process and the acquisition of a knowledge system.

References:

1. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан "Об утверждении национальной программы по развитию народного образования в 2022-2026 годах", от 11 мая 2022 года №УП-134.
2. Беляева, Ж.В. Обучение учащихся основной школы естественнонаучным методам познания на основе межпредметных связей биологии, химии и физики: диссертация ... д-ра пед. наук: 13.00.02/Ж.В.Беляева. -М., 2015. - 233с.

3. Гилёва,

А.В.

Межпредметный проект как средство реализации воспитательной компоненты. Методические рекомендации педагогам/ А.В. Гилёва. - Югорск, 2015. - 33 с.

4. Гурьев, А.И. Теория и практика системного подхода при реализации межпредметных связей в процессе обучения [Электронный ресурс]/ А.И. Гурьев.-Режим доступа:<http://www.biysk.secna.ru/jurnal/n4-5-2000/metodika/gurev.doc>.

5. Дубицкая, Л.В. Методическая система подготовки учителя к реализации педагогической интеграции в естественнонаучном образовании учащихся средней школы: диссертация... д-ра пед. наук: 13.00.02/ Л.В. Дубицкая. -Москва, 2016. -398 с.

6. Ле Тхи Киеу Оань. Естественнонаучный проект как средство реализации межпредметных связей в обучении физике// Тхи Киеу Оань Ле// Школа будущего. - 2020. - № 4. - С. 56-71.

7. Ле Тхи Киеу Оань. Модель урока решения задач межпредметного содержания/ Н.С. Пурышева, Тхи Киеу Оань Ле// Школа будущего. - 2020. - №. -С.16-26.

